

MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES OF FACIAL INDEX IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Scientific article describes age-related morphometric changes of facial index in children of primary school age. The results of the research show that all the craniometric indicators of the face of the skull in children of primary school age grow faster and faster in boys than in girls.*

Keywords: *face index, age-related morphometric changes, primary school children, upper face width, cheek diameter.*

INTRODUCTION

The social policy implemented during the last five years made it possible to systematically protect motherhood and childhood, as a result of which the reduction of maternal and infant mortality was achieved. At the same time, it is necessary to organize a system of targeting medical care in remote areas, increase the efficiency of medical services provided to mothers and children, further improve ambulatory care, develop urgent and specialized medical care, introduce medical genetics and modern screening programs is being done.

The anthropological study of growth processes in children living in different geographical zones, as well as in different conditions, is important in solving the problems of human ecology and medical geography.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Body mass, body length (height) and other longitudinal, transverse and circumferential measurements are taken into account in human morphology and especially in determining the level of physical development. Based on them, standard scales were created that allow determining the level of physical development in different groups of people and population.

Data collected during the anthropometric study are subjected to statistical (biometric) processing. Anthropometric data are widely used in the assessment of the impact of various socio-economic and other activities on the physical development and health of the population.

In order to analyze the morphometric changes of the facial index in children of junior school age, to study the periods of formation, the laws of growth and development, and in order to identify the cases of lagging behind in physical development, craniometric measurements were carried out in children aged 7-12 years living in Izboskan district of Andijan region. 180 physically and mentally healthy boys and girls of primary school age (7-12 years old) living in Izboskan district were taken as the material of the research. During the measurement of craniometric indicators, craniometric points recommended by Marthin R. (1928) were used.

The upper width of the face is the distance between the fronto-molar-temporal (fmt) points on the right and left sides. Measured with a barbell.

Cheek diameter is the maximum distance between the outer surfaces of the cheek arches on both sides of the head. This indicator was measured with a caliper in the direction of the frontal axis between the right and left zygion (zy) points.

Cheek diameter is determined by measuring the greatest width of the face, that is, the distance between the most protruding points of the cheek arch using a special circle.

Facial index – upper face width*100
cheek width

Figure 1. Area of measurement of the upper width of the face

Figure 2. Cheek diameter measuring area

RESULTS

The facial index decreases in boys at the age of 7-10 years. It increases relatively at the age of 11-12. In girls, the face index increases between the ages of 7-10. Later, among 11-12-year-olds, it decreases by 1.1 times.

In boys of primary school age, the craniometric indicators of the facial part of the skull increase rapidly, and the ratio of the facial part of the skull to the brain increases. In girls, as the

age increases, the growth of the craniometric parameters of the face slows down, and the ratio of the skull to the face of the brain decreases. The facial index decreases with age in both genders.

Table 1

***Growth dynamics of morphometric indicators of facial index in children of junior school age
 (in $X \pm m$, cm)***

Child's age	Gender	Craniometric parameters
		Face index
7 years old	Boy	100,01
	Girl	100,18
8 years old	Boy	99,20
	Girl	100,68
9 years old	Boy	99,32
	Girl	102,6
10 years old	Boy	100,44
	Girl	102,96
11 years old	Boy	99,18
	Girl	101,38
12 years old	Boy	100,50
	Girl	100,62

CONCLUSION

All craniometric indicators of the facial part of the skull grow faster and faster in boys than in girls. From 7 to 12 years old, both boys and girls have a decrease in the face index. This age transition is explained by the acceleration of the growth of the cheek diameter and the slowdown of the growth of the upper face width.

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